

ROLE OF POSITIVE-NEGATIVE RELIGIOUS COPING AND PERCEIVED SOCIAL SELF-EFFICACY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF RELATIONSHIP SATISFACTION AMONG MARRIED INDIVIDUALS

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Abstract

Objective: This research focused on determining the influence of positive-negative religious coping and perceived social self-efficacy on the level of relationship satisfaction an individual has in their current relationship. Prior research has established connections between both positive and negative religious coping and overall wellbeing separately, however this study aimed to assess how well the three factors combined to predict the level of satisfaction that married people were experiencing within the context of their marriage. Methodology: A quantitative, cross-sectional, correlational study was conducted to collect data. Participants were 224 married individuals, who were recruited through a purposive sampling method, and they completed the relationship satisfaction questionnaire, the brief religious coping scale, and a perceived social self-efficacy questionnaire. Using Pearson's correlation coefficients and multiple linear regression analyses performed with SPSS, data were analyzed to assess the relationship between all three constructs. Findings: Through bivariate correlation analysis, it was found that perceived social self-efficacy (0.64, $p < 0.01$), positive religious coping ways (0.23, $p < 0.01$), and negative religious coping ways (0.20, $p < 0.01$) all demonstrated statistically significant positive correlations with relationship satisfaction as indicated by the p value. The results of the multiple regression analyses also indicated that the model as a whole (0.41) was predictive of relationship satisfaction; however, only perceived social self-efficacy was identified as a statistically significant unique predictor (Beta= 0.61, $p < 0.001$). Positive religious coping and negative religious coping did not provide additional variance in the trends of marital relationship satisfaction when controlled for self-efficacy. Conclusion: The overall findings suggest that while both positive and negative religious coping were associated with relationship satisfaction, the main predictor

of the amount of satisfaction an individual has in their current relationship was how much they believe they can successfully cope with their social and emotional life effectively that is perceived social self-efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

Psychology has extensively researched two concepts, Religious Coping and Self-Efficacy, for their impact on personal adjustments, overall well-being, and social relationship dynamics, as they pertain to how an individual utilizes religious tradition and/or beliefs and practices to aid in reducing one's stress and pressure and/or handle life's many troubles (Pargament et al. in Ano & Vasconcelles, 2005). Current Models of Religious Coping (and Spiritual Coping) examine both Positive Religious Coping (i.e., seeking divine support, benevolent reinterpretation of circumstances, and working in harmony with the Divine) versus Negative Religious Coping (i.e., feeling disconnected from one's faith, imposing punishment by interpreting one's faith negatively and creating discord through faith within interpersonal relationships) (Pargament et al., 1998) as described in spirituality literature). Positive Religious Coping is often associated with positive psychological outcomes while Negative Religious Coping is frequently related to an individual's lack of emotional adjustment and lower levels of happiness in Life overall (Park et al., 2018). The term Self-Efficacy refers to one's belief in their capacity to competently create, plan and execute the series of actions necessary to overcome potential challenges and/or obstacles to success and has a direct influence on how an individual interacts with his/her goals, obstacles and close interpersonal relationships (Bandura, 1997). Perceived social self-efficacy was well-defined as confidence that an individual have on their ability to fruitfully involve in social activity based tasks that were considered essential to initiate and retain interactive relationships (Smith & Betz, 2000). With regard to Interpersonal Relationships, Self-Efficacy in Relational functioning is referred to as an individual's confidence in his/her ability to be an active participant in the maintenance and development of a healthy, functional relationship with another person as well as the ability to resolve

conflicts and enhance social interactions (Zhan et al., 2022)

Religious Coping: Definitions and Psychological Outcomes

Pargament et al. (1998) found that positive and negative religious coping represent two different coping strategies, each with its own distinct psychological correlates. Positive religious coping is characterized by a secure relationship with the sacred, seeking spiritual support, and viewing life stressors through a lens of benevolence. Negative religious coping is characterized by spiritual struggle, ambivalence about faith, and conflict with one's religious community. A longitudinal study found that individuals who employed positive religious coping demonstrated higher psychological well-being and greater adaptive outcomes over time, while individuals who used negative religious coping showed an increased risk of developing depressive symptoms as well as experiencing increased distress and diminished self-esteem. The presence of a negative religious coping strategy has consistently been linked with decreased life satisfaction and well-being in both clinical and general population studies (Breitbart et al., 2008; Hebert et al., 2009). Negative religious coping also appears to reduce an individual's ability to adaptively create meaning and regulate emotions, and, in addition, has been shown to promote an increased capacity for resilience. Coping self-efficacy may mediate the relationship between religious coping and emotional distress (Park et al., 2018; Dolcos et al., 2021).

Self-Efficacy and Relationship Satisfaction

Supervised research in Social Psychology has identified the role that Self-Efficacy plays in relationships. Those with greater levels of self-efficacy (particularly in Relationships) exhibit more positive relationship behaviors. These behaviors typically enhance the quality of Relationships, including: Effective Communication; Conflict

Resolution; and, Mutual Support. Greater Levels of Relationship Self-Efficacy correlate with Greater Relationship Satisfaction because individuals can successfully meet the demands of relationships (i.e. Challenges). Among partners in Romantic Relationships, studies have shown that Higher Levels of Self-Efficacy correlate with Greater Stability and Satisfaction in Romantic Relationships by enhancing Positive Behaviors and enabling Partners to respond Adaptively to Conflict and Stress (Woreta et al., 2025). Additionally, Relationship Self-Efficacy has been identified as an important Resource for Understanding Relationship Health as Relationship Self-Efficacy correlates with Life Satisfaction and Psychological Well-being through Relationship Experiences (Ami et al., 2025).

Intersections Between Religious Coping, Self-Efficacy, and Relationship Satisfaction

There has been considerable research on each of the constructs; however, there is limited research examining the interaction of these constructs and their effect on relationship satisfaction. Theoretical models of religious coping and self-efficacy suggest that one's religious coping influences one's perception of their own self-efficacy (e.g., coping self-efficacy) through the individual's emotional resources, interpretive frameworks, and confidence in their ability to manage stress (Krok, 2015). An individual who engages in positive religious coping may find meaning in their coping, the support and community provided by the religious community, which would then provide increased confidence in their ability to cope and engage constructively with their partner, enhancing their relational functioning and relationship satisfaction (Birhan & Eristu, 2023). On the other hand, individuals who engage in negative religious coping, such as individuals who are struggling spiritually or dissatisfied with their religion, may experience decreased confidence in their ability to cope and their ability to effectively engage in their relationships. When an individual believes that their stressor is divine punishment or feels disconnected from their religious community, this may reduce their belief in their own coping abilities and ability to constructively engage with their

partner, thus negatively affecting their relationship satisfaction (Pirutinsky, 2024).

There is a need for additional research examining the specific pathways that exist between these constructs in relationship contexts; however, the research on religious coping and overall well-being and self-efficacy in terms of relationship outcomes provide strong rationale for hypothesizing that positive religious coping and high self-efficacy are positively associated with relationship satisfaction and that negative religious coping may reduce both self-efficacy and relationship satisfaction (Howard et al., 2023). The vast majority of the research literature supports a similar theory/model in which a combination of both positive (religious) coping methods and increased self-efficacy contribute positively to an individual's overall relationship satisfaction. Positive religious coping methods act as a support to enhance a person's perception of their own self-efficacy and overall wellbeing; thus providing both a supportive means of creating a healthy, stable, and satisfying relationship, while negative religious coping methods act as a hindrance to create stress, uncertainty, and a diminished sense of self-confidence, which leads to a deterioration in relationship quality (Skalski-Bednarz et al., 2022). In addition to determining whether evidence exists for the two independent variables mentioned above, additional studies are necessary to explore other pathways through longitudinal and mediator analyses.

Objectives

To identify relationship between positive-negative religious coping, perceived social self-efficacy and relationship satisfaction among married individuals. To find positive-negative religious coping and perceived social self-efficacy as the predictor of relationship satisfaction among married individuals.

Research Design

The current research study employed a cross-sectional, and correlational research design in the study to analyze the predictive nature of religious coping and perceived social self-efficacy on relationship satisfaction among married individuals.

Participants

The sample was composed of 224 married person. The respondents must be adult and married and at the time of data collection. The time since marriage must be at least 6 months to 2 years. This was based on the inclusion criteria where participants needed to be legally married and living with their spouse. Those with severe psychological or marital crises (e.g., divorce in progress) were excluded.

Sampling Technique

Participants had been recruited using a non-probability purposive sampling approach. This approach was chosen as it will enable the researcher to select the respondents who fit into certain criteria that would be of interest with reference to the research purposes. Purposive sampling is usually applied in psychological studies where there is need to gain access to a given population.

Research Instruments

The following 3 scales were used in the current study.

The Perceived Social Self-Efficacy Scale (PSSE)

Perceived social self-efficacy was assessed by Perceived Social Self-Efficacy Scale designed by Smith and Betz (2000). The scale contains 25 items on 5 point Likert-type. This scale evaluates the confidence of individuals in dealing with interpersonal relations and social contact and preservation of relationships. The scale has shown a high level of internal consistency and construct validity.

Brief Religious Coping Scale (Brief RCOPE)

The Brief RCOPE created by Pargament et al. (1998) was used to determine the level of religious coping. This scale is related to positive (e.g., seeking spiritual support) and negative (e.g., spiritual discontent) religious coping. The scale has 14 items

with 4 point Likert scale. The Brief RCOPE has been extensively applied and demonstrates good psychometric characteristics in a variety of cultural backgrounds.

Relationship Questionnaire Scale (RSQ)

The Relationship Questionnaire (RSQ) developed by Bartholomew and Horowitz (1991) was used to measure styles of attachment. The scale had 30 items on 5 point Likert. The RSQ evaluates adult attachment orientations in terms of secure, fearful, preoccupied and dismissing attachment styles. The participants were rated on their concurrence with statements that indicate relationship beliefs and relationship behaviors. RSQ has proven to be reliable and acceptable in terms of validity in relationship investigation in adults.

Procedure

After receiving informed consents from the participants, the data were collected. The participants were informed on the objectives of the study, guaranteed of a sense of confidentiality, and told that they were free to participate in the study. The scales were used in both printed and electronic form based on the convenience of the participants. Respondents were made to answer the questionnaires truthfully and were given time to fill in the questionnaires. A high level of ethical considerations was emphasized during the research. Anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were ensured and no personal information was taken. The research followed the code of ethics of psychological studies that involve human subjects.

Data Analysis

The analysis of data was done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The Pearson correlation analysis was used to test relationships between variables whereas prediction was measured using regression analysis.

Results

Table 1 Correlations among Perceived Self-Efficacy, Relationship Satisfaction, Positive Religious Coping, and Negative Religious Coping (N = 224)

Variables	1	2	3	4
1. Perceived Social Self-Efficacy	—			

2. Relationship Satisfaction	.64**	—		
3. Positive Religious Coping	.26**	.23**	—	
4. Negative Religious Coping	.29**	.20**	-.10	—

The correlation analysis indicated a significant positive correlation between perceived self-efficacy and relationship satisfaction ($r = .64$), as shown by the statistical significance ($p < .01$) of these results, suggesting that as individuals experience an increase in perceived self-efficacy, their level of satisfaction with their relationships also increases. There were small-to-moderate positive correlations between perceived self-efficacy and both positive and negative religious copings ($r = .26$ and $.29$, respectively, $p < .01$ for both). Furthermore, relationship satisfaction was positively and significantly associated with both positive and negative religious copings ($r = .23$ and $.20$, respectively, $p < .01$). In summary, these results suggest that perceived self-efficacy, relationship satisfaction, and religious coping strategies are strongly related to each other in terms of how individuals use them to form positive relationships with those around them.

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis Predicting Relationship Satisfaction from Perceived Self-Efficacy and Positive-Negative Religious Coping (N = 224)

Predictor	B	SE B	β	t	p
Constant	21.72	4.94	—	4.39	< .001
Perceived Self-Efficacy	0.53	0.05	.61	10.76	< .001
Positive Religious Coping	0.24	0.18	.07	1.31	.190
Negative Religious Coping	0.07	0.11	.03	0.62	.535

Note. $R = .64$, $R^2 = .41$, Adjusted $R^2 = .41$. $F(3, 220) = 51.54$, $p < .001$.

Dependent variable = Relationship Satisfaction.

The aim of this study was to evaluate how perceived self-efficacy, positive religious coping, and negative religious coping predict relationship satisfaction. Using multiple linear regression analysis, there was a statistically significant prediction found, $F(3,220) = 51.54$, $p < .001$. Further, the three independent variables account for 41% of variance in relationship satisfaction ($R^2 = .41$).

Perceived self-efficacy was identified as an excellent and highly significant individual predictor for relationship satisfaction ($\beta = .61$, $p < .001$), thus, it can be said that better self-efficacy leads to enhanced relationship satisfaction. Positive religious coping ($\beta = .07$, $p = .190$) and negative religious coping ($\beta = .03$, $p = .535$) were not significant predictors of relationship satisfaction when allowing for the impact of self-efficacy.

Discussion

The relationships between perceived self-efficacy, relationship satisfaction and religious coping strategies were examined as well as their predictive effects on relationship satisfaction. Psychological self-efficacy was identified as a key component of relationship satisfaction while the influence of religious coping on relationship satisfaction was more modest when psychological self-efficacy was taken into consideration. Hypotheses were supported by evidence of a positive and strong relationship between psychological self-efficacy and relationship satisfaction. Furthermore, the results of the regression analyses confirmed that psychological self-efficacy was a significant predictor of relationship satisfaction. Therefore, it appears that people who have a high level of confidence in their ability to address and resolve challenges, manage their emotions, and develop solutions to

interpersonal conflicts are more likely to feel satisfied in their romantic relationships. In addition to being considered a major psychological resource for supporting adaptive functioning, resilience, and constructive communication, there are numerous studies that support the importance of self-efficacy for maintaining healthy relationships (Bandura, 1997). Finally, the large effect sizes observed in the present study are consistent with previous research demonstrating that higher levels of self-efficacy were associated with greater relationship adjustment and relationship satisfaction (Fincham et al., 2007). Positive religious coping was positively correlated with levels of Psychological Self-Efficacy and Relationship Satisfaction; however, these correlations were weak. This finding supports previous studies that found that Positive Religious Coping behaviours (e.g. seeking out spiritual support, seeing stressors as meaningful) can help foster both Emotional Well-Being (EWB) and Relational Harmony (RH) (Pargament et al., 2011). Nevertheless, Positive Religious Coping was not a significant predictor of Relationship Satisfaction according to the results of the regression analysis; this appears to indicate that although there was a bivariate relationship between Positive Religious Coping and Relationship Satisfaction, the unique contribution of Positive Religious Coping to Relationship Satisfaction diminished when taking into account the effects of Psychological Self-Efficacy. One explanation for this could be that Positive Religious Coping has an indirect (versus direct) impact on Relationship Satisfaction, through later developing Psychological Resources such as Psychological Self-Efficacy. Negative Religious Coping showed a positive correlation with both Psychological Self-Efficacy and Relationship Satisfaction; although these relationships were found to have weak to moderate strength. This finding is somewhat paradoxical, as the types of

Negative Religious Coping (i.e. Spiritual Struggle, experiences of punishment and/or dissatisfaction with a faith) have traditionally been identified as being related to less than optimal Psychological Outcomes (Pargament et al., 1998). However, it may be possible for an individual experiencing Negative Religious Coping to remain engaged in or rely on their own ability to be effectively cope (despite experiencing a struggle with their religious beliefs). In addition, it should be noted that Negative Religious Coping was not a significant predictor of Relationship Satisfaction according to the regression analyses. The fact that there is no significant and negative correlation between religious coping (positive) and religious coping (negative) supports the idea that these two styles of coping can be seen as separate styles as compared to being on two ends of the same continuum (Pargament et al., 2011). That means that when we study how religious coping contributes to psychological and relational development we should look at them separately. In summary, the results show that psychological self-efficacy is the main contributor to relationship satisfaction and accounts for most of the variance in our model. While religious coping correlates with relationship satisfaction, self-efficacy has greater predictive ability than religious coping does. Therefore, interventions to improve relationship satisfaction may have greater success by focusing on improving self-efficacy, problem-solving skills, and emotional regulation in individuals while also considering the role of religious coping in specific contexts.

Conclusion

The findings concluded that perceived social self-efficacy has a strong positive association with relationship satisfaction. Further, positive and negative religious coping also have positive but weak association with relationship satisfaction. Finally, perceived social self-efficacy predict relationship satisfaction whereas positive and negative religious coping has no impact on relationship satisfaction.

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